

The History of the Duchamp Opera House at St. Martinville, Louisiana

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Abstract

Original Research Article

The History of the Duchamp Opera House goes back to the early 1800s when David Sandoz, a native of Switzerland, arrived in the city of St. Martinville, Louisiana, United States. In the early 1800s, St. Martinville was filled with French Royal families who had fled their country's revolution. Wealthy visitors from New Orleans travelled there to escape the hot summer and the yellow fever epidemic. Today, the Duchamp Opera House has come full circle. St. Martinville's proud home for the arts supports regional artists and mercantile, and is the home of the Evangeline Players, and choral concerts by various church denominations during the Christmas season.

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INTRODUCTION

The History of the Duchamp Opera House goes back to the early 1800s when David Sandoz, a native of Switzerland, arrived in the city of St. Martinville, Louisiana, United States. In the early 1800s, St. Martinville was filled with French Royal families who had fled their country's revolution. Wealthy visitors from New Orleans traveled there to escape the hot summer and the yellow fever epidemic (Blitzer, 2001).

Background to Social Life

The reputation of *Le Petit Paris*--Little Paris,ⁱ for its refinement and cool summers attracted the affluent from New Orleans. Many of the best Creole families in the state made St. Martinville a fashionable summer resort. The artists of the French Opera and the French theaters in New Orleans also spent their vacations there. Each summer, the residents and visitors enjoyed concerts with selections from the best operas and performances of the witty comedies of the French repertoire. The entire season was a succession of lively amusement. Some theatrical artists married and made their homes in the city, giving the Little Paris on the Teche the flavor of a colony of professional and amateur musicians and actors (Delcambre, 1987).

Given the rich cultural inheritance of the growing population of St. Martinville and its environs, musical

activity should serve as a focus of interest. These were people who, it would seem, demanded many of the luxuries that they enjoyed elsewhere, which was reflected in the region's musical history (Knott, n.d.). Between 1820 and 1894, St. Martinville was bustling with great musical events. The New Orleans French Opera Company performed in St. Martinville as early as the last decade of the 18th century.ⁱⁱ Other memorable activities during this period were the grand concert performances by the famous Joseph Heine Troupe. This troupe was composed of artists who won fame throughout the United States. Visits by these troupes served as excuses for extended celebrations, as illustrated by the accounts of the day-long festivals that were occasioned in part by the presence in the town of the Southern Medical Company of New Orleans.ⁱⁱⁱ

The Excelsior Brass Band of St. Martinville contributed to the social and entertainment life in the city through several performances. The band also organized a steamboat excursion from New Iberia. The band furnished music to the excursionist.^{iv} Three major bands contributed immensely to this culture--the Excelsior Brass Band, the Union Brass Band, and the Greig Brass Band. Most of the talented amateur musicians received their training locally. There were years in which the brass bands became an established form of American musical entertainment, and in this respect, *Le Petit Paris* was perhaps more American in its socio-cultural life.^v Many amateur musicians enlivened the town in the closing decades of the 19th

century. One of these musicians was Miss Marie Rose Delahoussaye, who, as an organist for the town's venerable Catholic Church, played an impressive list of major works on that instrument.^{vi}

The Opera House

The Duchamp Opera House was erected to accommodate the abundance of socio-cultural life in St. Martinville. The town once had three opera houses in which performers from worldwide entertained. These

performances were followed by balls where barons, marquises, counts, and countesses wore bejeweled costumes and danced the minuet. The Duchamp Opera House was the newest and largest of the three opera houses.^{vii} The building was designed and built between the 1830s and 1840s by David Francois Sandoz, who came to America as a child from Switzerland. He was a master carpenter and began constructing a legacy of buildings in St. Martinville (Delhomme, 1998). Sandoz built his opera house and the New Era Hotel next door with bricks hand-made of clay from Bayou Teche.^{viii}

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The opera house was on the second story of the building. The upstairs was always intended for entertainment. Sandoz operated a feed and seed store, a grocery store, and later a mercantile store on the first floor. The second floor originally had four fireplaces, two on each side, and windows and French doors that opened onto a gallery on the north side of the building. The plaster walls contained elaborate moldings, and the floor was wood.^{ix}

The opera house was notable for hosting fundraisers and grand balls. One fundraiser was for the town's first hand-pump fire wagon following the Great Fire of 1856. The opera house was instrumental in saving a great part of the city during the fire. A ballet performance was going on upstairs when the fire started. The people formed a bucket brigade from Bayou Teche two blocks away, saving the building and the two adjacent ones.^x Other fundraiser events took place at the opera house, such

as the one for a new organ at St. Martin de Tours Catholic Church in St. Martin Square across the street. The wooden floor was made of candle wax to make it easier to dance at the ball.^{xi}

David Sandoz died in 1877, and his wife, Claire Christine Labbe, died in 1878. Their only surviving child, Marie Amelie Sandoz Duchamp, inherited the opera house, the two adjoining buildings, the Duchamp House across the street, and the plantation house. The opera house known as Duchamp Hall continued as a place of entertainment until she died in 1913.^{xii} That year, Dr. Bienvenu's father, Reuben Bienvenu, and two uncles, Zerben H. Bienvenu and Willie J. Bienvenu, purchased the property from Duchamp's heirs. The three brothers returned to St. Martinville from military service and on March 15, 1918, opened Bienvenu Bros., a departmental store. Their slogan was "Leaders of Fashion."^{xiii}

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The Bienvenu departmental store was a dry goods store with clothes for men, ladies, and children. Shoes, hats, housewares, linens, piece goods, and lotions were also sold in the store. It carried everything from baby clothes to burial clothes.^{xiv} When the store opened in 1918, it had a fine millinery department with an in-house milliner to design and decorate the most up-to-date ladies' hats. The Bienvenu brothers carried the finest brand-name merchandise from wholesale houses in New Orleans, Dallas, and St. Louis to New York.^{xv}

The Bienvenus removed the old galleries from the building and added a modern brick storefront. The original stairs to the second-floor opera house were outside the building from a carriageway to the south. The Bienvenus added interior stairs leading to the upstairs departments.^{xvi}

Willie J. Bienvenu died in the 1930s, leaving no heirs. The other two brothers and some of their children operated the successful business until 1994. Dr. Bienvenu worked in the store from nine years old until he entered medical school. He retired in 1996 after practicing as a family doctor for forty-three years.^{xvii} Dr. Bienvenu believes that the business was a huge success. The store gave some people the opportunity to work. Some of their staff went on to establish their businesses.^{xviii}

The family finally decided to close the business in 1994, when Wal-Mart came to St. Martinville. Wal-Mart forced three other departmental stores with a couple of gift shops and a lumber yard to close down.^{xix} Thus, on August 27, 1998, the surviving heirs of Reuben and Zerben H. Bienvenu donated the building to the city of St. Martinville.^{xx}

The city's government had several projects in 1998; however, the Old Opera House was the biggest. The government had in mind to extend to Main Street. This cultural icon should hopefully attract tourists to Main Street, not just near the Oak. The large red brick building will have a two-fold purpose. The downstairs will be an antique mall, while the upstairs will be the opera house. The intention was to restore the building to its original state as conceived by David Sandoz in the early 19th century (Payton, 1998).

Kathy Gerami, the project manager, explained that the paneling was removed from the walls downstairs, and the floor there was lifted. She noted the wooden floor sat on mud. However, no major structural adjustment was made to complete the project on time.^{xxi}

The restoration of the building began with money from the city and state funding from the Atchafalaya Basin Project, a program to preserve and open up tourism in the area.^{xxii} The Mayor, Eric Martin, announced the city received a \$50, 000 rural development grant from the Governor's office to help with repairs and renovations to the one-hundred-and-sixty-year-old building.^{xxiii} St. Martinville city contributed \$193, 600, while \$525, 818 came from the Department of Natural Resources (Nelson, 2000).

The refurbishing and fundraising for the opera house were not without a hitch. The Louisiana Contractors Association halted the project when it asserted the city circumvented the public bid laws in December 1998. The

mayor felt that the city could have contracted the project by itself, which may have saved them a whopping sum of \$150, 000. The city had been using volunteers from the community for much of the work, including volunteers from the St. Martin Parish Sheriff's Office trusty labor pool. The hundred-and-sixty-year-old building had a major setback, and work was halted for a while (Delhomme, 1999). The City Council was to decide during its December 20, 1999, meeting, how it would proceed with the bids, or if it would continue with the project. Unfortunately, the matter was not brought before the Council because of the December trip of several city officials to Goree Island on the West Coast of Africa, where African-American ancestors were transported to the New World as slaves. Work resumed on the site in early 2000.^{xxiv}

The renovation was extensive. Workmen had to remove an old wooden floor and dig out eighteen inches of mud to pour a new foundation. Innumerable artifacts were found predating the Civil War. They found slate from the original roof, a silver spoon, shards of china, pieces of wine glasses, wine bottles, hand-forged latches, and even a piece of the original stair railing.^{xxv} At the southeast corner near the ceiling on the floor, workers found a steel beam made by the Carnegie Steel Company in the mid-1800s. Written on the beam in French script were the words, "Duchamp Hall, St. Martinville." This discovery clarified the confusion about the initial name of the building when Sandoz built it.^{xxvi}

The workers removed old paneling from the walls upstairs to discover elaborate plasterwork, even on the ceiling, where the original lathing was still intact. When they removed the paneling that had covered the original plaster walls, they found signatures of people who had put on performances and dates. A few of the signatures were of local people like Judge Felix Voorhies, a famous playwright and poet, whose plays were performed at the opera house. The signature of local pianist Louis Olivier appears many times. He was a frequent accompanist in the early 1900s.^{xxvii}

The attic was an architect's delight with massive Norman truss beams. Sandoz probably built the building the way things were in Switzerland, because he came from there. Workers found on the property an old beehive cistern that predates the building, as well as the brick base where the exterior stairway to the opera house had stood.^{xxviii}

The renovated building, now called the Old Opera House, was officially opened on October 21, 2000. Before then, Troy Frick Construction of Lake Charles was expected to hand over the keys between October 13 and 16. The total cost of renovating the structure was around \$854, 000 (Landry, 2000). The opening ceremony was attended by city, parish, and state officials who presided over the ribbon-cutting ceremony (Bienvenu, 2001).

In January 2001, the Evangeline Players, a local theater troupe, performed "Driving Miss Daisy" to a full house on the second floor, now called the Duchamp Room. The building will be the official home of the Evangeline Players.^{xxix}

The Duchamp Opera House Interior

Some major adjustments were made during the renovation of the opera house. On the first floor, the divided stairway added by the Bienvenus was dismantled and rebuilt at the back. The downstairs was designed to be an antique mall, while the second storey will be the opera house, just as David Sandoz had initially conceived it in the 1800s.^{xxx} The city estimates that twelve antique merchants will occupy the downstairs.^{xxxi}

CONCLUSION

Today, the Duchamp Opera House has come full circle. St. Martinville's proud home for the arts supports regional artists and mercantile and is the home of the Evangeline Players.^{xxxii} The 2002 Calendar of the opera house consists of Main Street Beauty Pageant, "Wedding from Hell" by Acadia Players, Evangeline Players Summer Drama Camp, "Prisoner of Second Avenue" by Neil Simon, "Kingfish" by Acadia Players, "Supper on the Square" by the Evangeline Players, "Steel Magnolias" by the Evangeline Players, City's of St. Martinville Volunteer Banquet, and choral concerts by various church denominations during the Christmas season.^{xxxiii}

Acknowledgment

The data used in writing this article were derived from several secondary sources, including newspaper clips, unpublished manuscripts, and the internet, obtained from the St. Martinville Public Library in Louisiana, United States. The Duchamp Opera House also provided additional source materials, such as the Calendar of events.

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ⁱ St. Martinville was popularly known as "Le Petit Paris" in the early 19th century because of its flamboyant social life and resort atmosphere.

ⁱⁱ (Knott, n.d.), 8.

ⁱⁱⁱ (Knott, n.d.), 8.

^{iv} (Knott, n.d.), 8.

^v (Knott, n.d.), 9.

^{vi} (Knott, n.d.), 9.

^{vii} (Blitzer, 2001), 1.

^{viii} (Blitzer, 2001), 1.

^{ix} (Blitzer, 2001), 1.

^x (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.

^{xi} (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.

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xvii (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.
xviii (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.
xix (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.
xx (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.
xxi (Payton, 1998), 1.
xxii (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.

xxiii (Payton, 1998), 1.
xxiv (Delhomme, 1999), 3.
xxv (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.
xxvi (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.
xxvii (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.
xxviii (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.
xxix (Blitzer, 2001), 12H.
xxx (Payton, 1998), 1.
xxxi (Delhomme, 1999), 6A.
xxxii Source unknown, "Duchamp Opera House Histoire," in www.duchamp-operahouse.com/A_pages/Histoire.htm.
xxxiii 2002 Calendar of Events at the Duchamp Opera House.